

Narrative Review

Association Between Cancers and Multiple Sclerosis

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ABSTRACT

Multiple sclerosis (MS) is a chronic inflammatory disease of central nervous system (CNS) which is supposed that genetic, environmental, and infection history play a pivotal role in its pathogenesis. Cancer, on the other hand, is characterized with abnormal growth and proliferation of cells which its risk factors are similar to MS. In this setting, accumulating lines of evidences have recently showed a controversial results regarding correlation of malignancies and MS. Although these two diseases are similar in some aspects of their pathogenesis, most of epidemiological studies show a reduced overall cancer risk among MS patients or no differences between them and general population, suggesting protective effects of autoimmune diseases such as MS against cancers. Although the exact etiology of neither MS nor cancers is known completely, previous studies showed some associations between them based on both epidemiological and experimental investigation. Therefore, in this study we reviewed associations between cancer and MS, using current experimental and clinical evidences.

Keywords: multiple sclerosis; cancer, autoimmunity, inflammation.

Introduction

Multiple sclerosis (MS) is an autoimmune disease of central nervous system (CNS) with genetic, environmental, and infection history known as its risk factors(1). Cancer, on the other hand, is characterized with abnormal growth and proliferation of cells with risk factors similar to that of MS. There are many evidences in the medical literature which indicate important role of genetics in pathogenesis of both cancer and autoimmune diseases. Furthermore, viruses are considered as one of the most important factors in the etiology of MS; similarly most of studies that have been done on gastric carcinoma, NPC, and LPD's, showed

viruses, especially Epstein - Barr virus (EBV), may take part in emergence of epithelial tumors, although this has not been observed in breast cancer(2-5). Even though many epidemiological studies have been done with regards to determining the prevalence of cancer among MS patients and therefore finding any association between them, their results are controversial and generally we can divide them to two major parts as some of them show decreased risk of cancer among MS patients(6-8) which shows a protective effect of MS, lowering the risk of cancer which was be supported by an experimental study that suggested autoimmune haplotype can protect against some cancers (9). On

the other hand, some of the studies concluded that there is no differences in the overall risk of cancers between MS patients and general population (10, 11); and to the best of our knowledge, there is only one study that showed an increased overall cancer risk among MS patients (12). Furthermore, many studies have been carried out in regards to cancer risk among autoimmune diseases other than, but similar to MS, though they could not come to a consensus about association between them(13, 14). So in this study we decided to shed a light on possible linkage between MS and cancers.

Experimental studies

One of the strongest rationalizations for association between cancers and autoimmune disease is based on mechanisms of pathogenesis of these two disorders. Although studies have not demonstrated the exact roles of inflammation in emergence of cancers, it has been shown that inflammation is one major factor in pathogenesis of multiple sclerosis, so it can suggest a possible association between them.

Anti-tumor immunity is mostly carried out by CD8+ cytotoxic T lymphocytes which are induced by Th cells, especially CD4+ Th1 cells producing IL-2 and gamma interferon. Continuity of this anti-tumor activity is supported by cytokines, which are secreted by dendritic cells such as IL-12, IL-15, and IL-18 (15). Although Th1 responses are necessary for induction and maintenance of anti-tumor immunity, most of clinical studies and flow cytometric analyses supported an abnormal Th1/Th2 ratio. In this regard, there are many evidences indicating a decreased Th1/Th2 ratio and a higher level of IL-4 and IL-10 but not IL-2 in cancer patients (16). Taken together, based on the evidence, we can conclude a dominant pattern of Th1 cells in most of cancer patients which may result from a reduced function of Th1 cells or over-activation of Th2 cells or both of them (15). On the contrary, other studies on treated patients showed that in cancer patients, levels of Th2 lymphocytes and cytokines decreased and also a switch from Th2 to Th1 responses occurred after treatment (17).

MS is an autoimmune disease of CNS which is characterized with inflammation and demyelination, and CD4+ cells play a major role in MS pathogenesis (18). Th1 cells secrete anti-inflammatory cytokines such as IL-4 and IL-10; conversely, Th2 cells produce inflammatory

cytokines such as INF- γ and TNF- α and since MS is an inflammatory disease, induction of Th1 related cytokines causes progression of inflammatory autoimmune diseases such as MS (19).

According to these data, in early stages of cancer when treatment is not started, cancer patients mostly have a Th2 pattern, so risk or progression of MS is low, but after the initiation of treatment, Th pattern switches from Th2 to Th1, so it might increase risk and progression of MS in cancer patients. However, similar inflammatory pathogenesis of these two disorders such as altered cytokine profile including increased IL-10 and TNF levels in MS patients can increase the risk of some hematological cancers among them, as these cytokines increase growth and proliferation of B cells which may lead to formation of tumor clones (20-22).

It has been estimated that viruses participate in 15%-20% of cancers worldwide and among them human papillomavirus (HPV), human T-cell lymphotropic virus 1 (HTLV-1), Epstein-Barr virus (EBV), human herpes virus 8 (HHV-8), hepatitis B virus (HBV) and hepatitis C virus (HCV) have the most important role in onset of cancers (23-25). Accumulating data, including animal model of MS (EAE) and MS patients investigations, demonstrated that viruses are involved in pathogenesis of MS acting as environmental factor, so in this regard, MS and cancers have some similarities.

Studies showed that higher latitude increases risk of MS and it is clear that at higher latitudes, people receive less sunlight, and it is proposed that sunlight affects melatonin production and vitamin D3 and hereby can suppress immune system, so maybe sun exposure has a protective effect on MS. Nowadays, it is accepted that constant exposure to sun is a major risk factor for development of skin cancer and since it has been shown that sun exposure has a protective effect on MS, maybe cancer patients have a lower risk of skin cancer (26).

Although previous studies such as clinical trials and epidemiological studies could not demonstrate beneficial effects of vitamin D3 on reducing the risks of cancer, other clinical and preclinical studies suggest vitamin D deficiencies as a risk factor for cancers. Similarly, there is a large amount of evidence that vitamin D is associated with the risk of multiple sclerosis, especially in studies which showed mechanism of action of vitamin D on

immune system. Taken together, vitamin D deficiency has a role in risks of cancers and multiple sclerosis and adding supplementary vitamin D might be beneficial for reducing co-occurrence of these two diseases in an individual.

Obesity has a positive association with risks of cancer and also epidemiological data suggest obesity as a cause of 14% of cancer deaths in men and up to 20% in women (27). Furthermore, it has been shown that obesity might have similar correlations with MS (28, 29), since a common mechanisms such as secretion of inflammatory markers from adipocytes occurs in both diseases.

Intravenous immunoglobulin (IVIG) is used for many autoimmune diseases and also its beneficial effects as a treatment for MS were shown in some studies (30, 31). Mechanism of action of IVIG in autoimmune diseases is mediated by altering Fc receptor and also blockade of it, modulating cytokine pattern, and neutralizing autoantibodies (32-34). IVIG is also used as a therapeutic method in cancers, especially hematological malignancies, as it causes increased activity of NK cells by increasing levels of IL-12 cytokine (35), inducing expression of Fas and proapoptotic genes which leads to decreased growth of malignant cells (36), and also inhibition of the production of matrix metalloproteinase-9 which inhibits tumor metastasis (37). Since IVIG is used in both cancer and MS patients and this treatment has a beneficial effect in both disorders, use of it in each of them can decrease risk of other in an individual.

Proto-oncogenes in normal conditions express proteins which play a major role in regulation of growth and proliferation of cells but after occurrence of mutation in them, their activities alter and cause malignancies. Recently, it has been shown that oncogenes in addition to malignancies, are also involved in autoimmune diseases such as systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE), as elevated levels of C-myc, C-myb, and C-ras were detected in them (20, 38).

Epidemiological studies

As most of previous studies investigated risk of comorbidity of MS with special types of cancer, we cannot conclude overall cancer rate among MS patients simply; however, investigation among previous studies showed that except one study (12),

almost all of them showed a lower or no differences of the overall cancer rate among MS patients.

In a study that was conducted in Eindhoven Cancer Registry, van de Schans et al. evaluated comorbidity of lymphoma with other autoimmune and chronic inflammatory disorders and found that there is a positive association between them, suggesting similarity in part of their pathogenesis (39).

Achiron et al.(6) reported prevalence of cancers among MS patients of Israeli population and in their study, they found reduced risk of cancer among women before initiation of immunomodulatory treatment and also during treatment. Although risk of cancer in females was lower than general population, immunomodulatory treatment increased risk of cancer in them which is in contrary with the hypothesis that hyperactivation of immune system in autoimmune diseases reduces susceptibility to cancers. In contrast with previous study in which sex-specific reduction has been shown in women, in a study in Danish of Denmark, Nielson et al. (8) found a reduction in risk of cancer in men, although cancer risk among women was not unusual. In addition, in another study, an overall reduced risk of cancer was observed in both males and females (7). In a similar study, it was observed that although risks of several types of cancer in MS patients are lower than general population, immunosuppressor (IS) treatment can increase risk of breast cancer in women (40).

In an interesting study which was carried out by Lebrun et al. (41), it has been shown that although overall cancer rate is lower among MS patients, immunosuppressor (IS) treatment and also duration of exposure can increase risk of cancer, suggesting that MS patients who receive IS treatment should be monitored regularly with respect to the development of cancers.

Previous studies showed an increased risk of some types of cancers, especially CNS tumors (12, 42) and breast cancers (10, 12). Increased risk of breast cancer among women with MS was suspected, due to previous recommendation for them which suggested that pregnancy can exacerbate the course of disease(43). On the other hand, increased risk of CNS tumors in MS patients might be resulted from inflammation in their brain, which were supported by neuroimaging of MS patients which suggests tumors of brain as an early diagnosis and also report

of increased risk of CNS tumors in MS patients who were treated with IS treatment (44). It should also be considered that diagnosis of MS patients using MRI and also regular clinical follow-up, can provide the conditions of diagnosis of CNS tumors which may lead to increased rate of co-morbidity of MS with other CNS tumors in epidemiological studies.

Conclusion

In summary, epidemiological studies show reduced overall cancer rate among MS patients, which can be divided in two parts: 1- Increased rate of CNS tumors in MS patients which may be resulted from inflammation due to pathogenesis of MS and 2- Decreased rate of outside CNS cancers in MS patients which may be resulted from an increased anti-cancer activity of immune system due to hyper activation of immune system in MS patients. On the other hand, experimental studies show similar mechanisms in some aspects of pathogenesis of these two disorders suggesting an increased co-morbidity of them.

Conflict of interest

None.

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